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ENGINEERING PROJECT TO FOSTER GLOBAL COMPETENCY AND ASSESSMENT OF LEARNING OUTCOMES USING THE PROG TEST

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ABSTRACT

We designed and have been executing a cross-cultural engineering project since 2013. This engineering educational project was designed to foster innovative and global engineers and scientists based on multidisciplinary, multinational, and industry-academia collaborative project-based learning. The students participated in the project were first-year graduates and third- and fourth-year undergraduates. There were various nationalities including Japanese, Thai, Indonesian, Cambodian, Malaysian, Vietnamese, Chinese, Singaporean, Mongolian, German, Polish, Dutch, and Brazilian. The project themes were related to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) such as energy, transportation, environment, poverty, natural disasters, and education as well as practical issues in industries. Multinational student teams were required to not only identify and define social, technical, and interdisciplinary problems but to design and prototype solutions as well.

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The quality assurance of the educational program was achieved by analysis of the results in (1) learning outcomes based on rubrics and (2) a generic skill assessment test of the PROG (Progress Report on Generic Skills). The PROG assesses competencies in working skills, personal skills, and problem-solving skills. It is one of the commonly used measurement methods introduced to 470 higher educational institutes in Japan. This paper shows comparative data of average PROG scores among global workers in Asia, model domestic workers, and university students. The global workers marked higher scores than other groups at all of the survey elements particularly in “relating with others,” “team management,” and “self-control.” Furthermore, it was proved that cross-cultural engineering project contributed to developing these three elements of competencies.

1 INTRODUCTION

In a society where rapid technological innovations and environmental changes are developing on a daily basis, the models of human resources developed in universities and field trainings are significantly changing. In the field of engineering education, the present goal is to develop human resources that can solve social issues, such as Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and create more innovations, including products and services with new values. Moreover, the development of soft skills, such as communication and leadership skills, is required in addition to the acquisition of in-depth knowledge and other professional skills.

Higher educational institutions have begun to incorporate the development of global competencies into their educational goals. For example, the Modularising Multilingual and Multicultural Academic Communication Competence project, which was funded by the European Commission, created a learning outcome index centered on linguistic communication, and it encouraged its use for assessments [1]. In addition, in North America, the Association of American Colleges and Universities (AAC & U) created the Global Learning VALUE Rubric and set six evaluation items [2]. Moreover, the Belief, Events, and Values Inventory (BEVI) [3], the Global Perspective Inventory (GPI) [4], the Intercultural Development Inventory (IDI) [5], and the Miville-Guzman Universality-Diversity Scale Short Form (MGUDS-S) [6] have been developed and used by many educational institutions in various countries to assess learning outcomes.

The global competency of human resources in science and engineering has gradually expanded from solely focusing on skills and knowledge to attitude and identity as the need for understanding and respecting different cultures and fields, and having a global perspective. Those dimensions are often overlapped with different areas of expertise. As a characteristic of engineering education, many previous studies have mentioned the necessity for the ability to perform professional work in a global environment. In other words, technical human resources are not only required to have specialized knowledge and skills, but they also need to have foreign language skills and the ability to adapt in intercultural environments and communicate with people from around the world while applying their skills and knowledge in practical workspaces.

In this study, an engineering educational project was designed to foster innovative and global engineers and scientists based on multidisciplinary, multinational, and industry–academia collaborative project-based learning. The quality assurance of the proposed project was achieved by analyzing the (1) learning outcomes based on specific rubrics and (2) a generic skill assessment test of the Progress Report on Generic (PROG) skills. The PROG assesses competencies in working skills, personal skills, and problem-solving skills. It was proven that the cross-cultural engineering project significantly contributed to the development of the above-mentioned four competency dimensions.

2 GLOBAL PROJECT-BASED LEARNING (PBL) FOR GLOBAL HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT

2.1 Global PBL

Human resources that demonstrate leadership and innovation in global environments are required. In addition, teamwork between people with different specialties, backgrounds, and cultures is now vital, as well as a methodology that can integrate the knowledge and skills among them. Thus, innovation for education including the methodologies and practical training that create new values is necessary for all human resources in science and engineering, and its implementation is required in all undergraduate and graduate schools.

As a training program for future engineers and scientists, Shibaura Institute of Technology annually implements 80 global PBL courses in Japan and overseas. Those courses can be categorized into two broad types. One is a single discipline type including mechanical engineering, electrical, and electronic information engineering, and construction engineering, and another is a cross-disciplinary type, which crosses multiple disciplines and fosters multidisciplinary students. The project themes for the cross-sectoral global PBL courses are relevant to social issues, such as the SDGs. Participants are demanded to investigate cross-sectoral problems and propose their solutions with innovation by tackling the serious issues in industries and local communities. Generally, those themes cover a wide range of sectors and industries, including energy, transportation, environment, poverty, natural disasters, and education. In cross-disciplinary PBL, students with various majors work together on problem finding and setting, proposing solutions, producing prototypes, and preparing presentations.

The authors launched a global PBL course in 2013 for students from Japan and Southeast Asia to develop human resources who can promote cross-disciplinary discoveries, the resolution of social issues, and innovation [7].

First, in collaboration with the Shibaura Institute of Technology (SIT) and King Mongkut's University of Technology Thonburi (KMUTT) in Thailand, a global PBL course was launched in Bangkok in February 2013, and the participants from Sepuluh Nopember Institute of Technology (ITS) in Indonesia were added to the program in the next year. The course was implemented multiple times in several years, and it resulted in many improvements, where it was applied for the eighth time

in February 2020. In addition, since 2015, KMUTT, ITS, and other universities from Japan, Thailand, Indonesia, Cambodia, Malaysia, Vietnam, Mongolia, China, Taiwan, India, Germany, the Netherlands, etc., have participated in the course in the SIT Omiya Campus in Japan. In addition, in 2017, another global PBL course was launched in Lisbon, Portugal, in cooperation among Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, SIT, and KMUTT.

The cross-cultural global PBL venues were expanded to three universities in Thailand, Japan, and Portugal as the Cross-Cultural Engineering Projects (CEPs) to be one of the modules in master's degree program of SIT's Graduate School of Science and Engineering. The main project themes are based on SDGs and various local issues in Thailand, corporate and community issues in Japan, and innovative creation in Portugal. There are differences in themes and team members in each course, however, the basic course structure for carrying out intensive activities for about 10 days is the same, and we expect the same educational effect on training global human resources.

2.2 Outline of Cross-Cultural Engineering Project at SIT

The outline of the CEP implemented at SIT Omiya Campus, Nasu Town, and Tochigi Prefecture is described in this section. It was implemented for 9 days from December 6 to 14, 2018 with 71 students and six teaching assistants who came from 21 universities in 11 countries.

Table 1. Process of the cross-cultural engineering project

Day 1	Opening Ceremony, Briefing and Ice Breaking Session Introduction of Project Themes, Assigning Groups
Day 2	Group Activities: problem identification and requirements analysis
Day 3	Group Activities: idea generation for solutions Design Review Group Activities: reflection and redesign
Day 4	Field Study and Workshop in Nasu Town
Day 5	Workshop and Group Presentation in Nasu Town
Day 6	Factory Tour at a Waste Treatment and Recycling Site
Day 7	Group Activities: building proposals or prototypes
Day 8	Group Activities: preparation for presentation Final Presentation
Day 9	Assessments Closing Ceremony

The CEP performed problem discovery, requirement definition, requirement analysis, and idea creation according to the systems engineering process, and it implemented comprehensive solution proposals (Table 1). During the course, an intermediate design review and a final presentation were held. The students gained experience in finding and solving problems and in prototyping in a multidisciplinary and multicultural environment. This experience is mainly a pre-experience of what science and engineering students may encounter in their future careers. In addition,

we introduced an environment that facilitates Internet of Things prototyping in this course. All of the CEPs were designed as PBL to promote student competency by taking into consideration the following aspects:

- (1) A multinational community must be established in a short period of time;
- (2) The issues must be narrowed down from the problem areas with a high degree of freedom;
- (3) The viewpoint of innovation should be emphasized;
- (4) Unforeseen situations similar to those in real-world projects should occur.

3 ASSESSMENT OF LEARNING OUTCOMES

3.1 Multidirectional Assessment for Learning Outcomes from the CEPs

A classification of the common learning outcomes for global human resource development was made independent of the studied subjects, where the learning outcomes corresponded to the different learning objectives of each subject, and the assessment tools were set for each learning outcome [8, 9].

The learning outcomes and tools introduced to the CEPs are the following:

- (1) Generic skills (PROG applied to global talent evaluation) [10, 11];
- (2) Engineering communication skills (developed a CEFR-based Can-Do list) [12];
- (3) Intercultural ability.

In addition, the following two items were set in accordance with the learning objectives that are specific to each subject:

- (4) Rubric for individual learning outcomes (used for student self-evaluation and student peer evaluation);
- (5) Rubric for the results of the team activities (peer evaluation between teams and evaluation by teachers).

The authors reported on the engineering communication skills (CEFR-based Can-Do lists) and the intercultural abilities [12], but this paper mainly focuses on the generic skills.

The quality assurance of the educational program was achieved by analysis of the results in learning outcomes based on rubrics and a generic skill assessment test of the PROG skills) [11]. The PROG assesses competencies in working skills, personal skills, and problem-solving skills. It is one of the commonly used measurement methods introduced to 455 higher educational institutes in Japan.

3.2 Global Competency Assessment Using PROG

The PROG test was developed to evaluate “literacy” as the ability to use knowledge as a cognitive ability and “competency” as the ability to use behavioral traits and decision-making skills as noncognitive abilities. Figure 1 shows the configuration of the PROG test. The authors have seen that competency of students have been greatly increased through active learning, such as PBL, and the discussion below focuses on the competencies in the generic skills.

The PROG competencies refer to those of high-performing business people. The authors analyzed the generic skills characteristics of global human resources by measuring the competencies of business people who worked overseas and

demonstrated high performance. Figure 2 shows the average competency of (1) global business people, the Japanese people who lived in other Asian countries for 4 years on average and were highly rated, (2) highly rated domestic business people, and (3) students. The business people with management experience who lived abroad had a higher competency score than the professionals who only worked in Japan. Generally, performing in a cross-cultural workplace requires a higher degree of job performance than working in a single culture. In particular, the three characteristics of global human resources are “relating with others,” which creates good relationships with others, “team management,” which asserts opinions in one place and leads to successful teams, and “self-control,” which makes people control their stress.

Fig. 1 Components of PROG

In the SIT, the PROG test was implemented for all of the first- and third-year undergraduate students and all of the first-year graduate students who were studying for a master’s degree in systems engineering and science. In addition, the PROG test was implemented for all of the participants at the completion of the Cross-CEP. To accommodate participants from other countries who do not know Japanese, English versions were available for both the PROG literacy and competency tests, and a Thai version was also available for the literacy tests. Moreover, the generic skills of all of the CEP participants were assessed, and the assessment of the learning outcomes was conducted for the students from the participating countries.

We evaluated how participation in the CEP contributed to fostering the students’ competencies. We also compared the PROG competency growth of the CEP students and the non-CEP students for the first-year master’s and third-year undergraduate students. Table 2 shows the comparison results of the first-year master’s students. In addition, we compared the increase in the competency score in the first year of undergraduate studies to the score in the first year of the master’s program or at the end of the CEP. Almost all of the competency scores have increased after students studying in the degree program with or without participation

in the CEP. Regarding the three elements of the global human resources, namely, “relating with others,” “team management,” and “self-control,” the competency scores of the CEP participants were higher than those of the other students who did not participate in the program.

Fig. 2. Validation of PROG in competency: Comparison of global model workers, domestic model workers, and students

Table 2. Score change of firs- year graduates who took part in the CEP (change of average scores)

1st year master	1st year master of CEP(FY2018) n=16			1st year master of non-CEP(FY2018) n=48			<CEP> minus <Non-CEP> =Exceed : ✓
	1st year	1year master	difference	1st year	1st year master	difference	
Comprehensive	3.50	4.31	0.81	3.19	3.79	0.60	✓
Teamwork	3.56	4.44	0.88	3.38	3.94	0.56	✓
Relation with others	4.00	4.81	0.81	3.50	3.79	0.29	✓
Collabration with others	3.31	3.94	0.63	3.38	4.29	0.92	
Team management	3.50	4.63	1.13	3.21	3.75	0.54	✓
Personal	3.69	4.06	0.38	3.33	3.60	0.27	✓
Self control	3.63	4.00	0.38	3.19	3.50	0.31	✓
Self confidence	3.63	3.81	0.19	3.42	3.60	0.19	
Behavior control	3.88	4.13	0.25	3.29	3.54	0.25	
Problem solving	3.88	4.63	0.75	4.13	4.71	0.58	✓
Problem identification	4.56	4.38	-0.19	4.31	5.02	0.71	
Planing solutions	3.56	4.69	1.13	3.90	4.23	0.33	✓
Implement solutions	3.69	4.06	0.38	4.00	4.58	0.58	

Table 3 shows the results of the third-year undergraduate students. We compared the increase in the competency scores in the first year of undergraduate studies with the scores at the completion of the CEP in the third year. Almost all of the

competency scores of the CEP participants were higher than those of the other students who did not participate in the program. In addition, regarding the three elements of the global human resources, namely, “relating with others,” “team management,” and “self-control,” the competency scores of the CEP participants were higher.

The College of Systems Engineering and Science and Graduate School of Systems Engineering and Science of SIT now systematically implement many PBL programs for undergraduate and master’s programs [13], and they have the opportunity to expand the students’ competencies in degree programs. In addition, the CEP participants have generally increased their competencies in comparison with other students.

Table 3. Score change of third-year undergraduates who took part in the CEP (change of average scores)

3rd year undergraduate	3rd year students of CEP(FY2018) n=7			3rd year students of non-CEP(FY2018) n=56			<CEP> minus <Non-CEP> = Exceed : ✓
	1st year	3rd year	difference	1st year	3rd year	difference	
Comprehensive	3.43	5.00	1.57	2.96	3.30	0.34	✓
Teamwork	4.43	5.29	0.86	3.04	3.41	0.37	✓
Relation with others	4.57	5.00	0.43	3.24	3.38	0.14	✓
Collaboration with others	4.86	4.43	-0.43	3.15	3.52	0.37	
Team management	3.71	5.57	1.86	3.00	3.55	0.55	✓
Personal	2.71	4.57	1.86	3.20	3.55	0.35	✓
Self control	2.86	5.60	2.74	3.49	3.75	0.26	✓
Self confidence	2.43	5.40	2.97	3.00	3.34	0.34	✓
Behavior control	3.43	3.71	0.29	3.09	3.55	0.46	
Problem solving	3.29	4.29	1.00	3.76	4.07	0.31	✓
Problem identification	2.86	4.29	1.43	3.89	4.27	0.38	✓
Planing solutions	3.43	3.86	0.43	3.64	3.59	-0.05	✓
Implement solutions	3.14	4.80	1.66	3.79	4.25	0.46	✓

4 CONCLUSION

In order to foster science and engineering human resources that are capable of innovation in global environments, competencies were set based on surveys conducted in Japan and overseas, and a global PBL course was designed for human resource development, which was expanded gradually in Japan and overseas. Furthermore, the system was structured by classifying the learning objectives into general-purpose learning objectives that do not depend on subjects and those that are specific to subjects, and a system for assessing the learning outcomes in multiple aspects was constructed and evaluated.

The working person competency with high performance in a global environment was evaluated in the PROG test. As a result, the three competencies, namely, “relating with others,” “team management,” and “self-control,” were identified as the characteristics of the global human resources. We also designed and introduced the

Cross-CEP to develop global competencies in undergraduate and graduate degree programs. From the evaluation results in the PROG test, it was confirmed that the CEP students had higher scores when it comes to the above-mentioned three competencies in comparison with the non-CEP students.

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